

9 PLANETS IN SEVENTH BHAVA & SEVENTH LORD IN 12 BHAVAS

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Abstract:

Seventh bhava is very important bhava. It gives best life partner, business partner and social status. Every planet gives unique result in Seventh bhava. Similarly seventh lord gives unique result in 12 bhavas. By understanding this, marriage matching is very easy for us.

Key Words: Sun, Moon, Mars, Mercury, Jupiter, Venus, Saturn, Rahu, Kethu, Seventh Bhava, Seventh Lord, First Bhava, Second Bhava, Third Bhava, Fourth Bhava, Fifth Bhava, Sixth Bhava, Seventh Bhava, Eighth Bhava, Ninth Bhava, Tenth Bhava, Eleventh Bhava, Twelfth Bhava .

Introduction:

An isolated person should not be respected in the universe. A man with good friends, good partners and good spouse is honoured by the society. Seventh bhava and Seventh bhava lord are most important for that.

Nine Planets in Seventh Bhava:

Sun in Seventh Bhava:

Spouse would come from powerful family with good character. His/ her eyes and face are very beautiful. He / She has political interest. If Sun standing rasis are Aries or Leo, it is very auspicious one. First night (Nishegam) should not be done on the wedding day. Wedding will be done at temple is good. After the born of Second child, promotion would come. After marriage growth will be developed.

Moon in Seventh Bhava:

Mother's relative would come as a spouse. Spouse has some bad habits. Marriage done at earlier age. After marriage transfer should come. Spouse has done night duty. If Jupiter aspects moon, there will be raining on the wedding day.

Mars in Seventh Bhava:

Spouse has more properties with physical fitness. Spouse will do uniformed service like police, army, etc... Spouse would be a rowdy. The native has a scar on his abdomen area. After marriage the native buy properties. Spouse would come via brother's relatives. Spouse would born on Tuesday or the starts of Mars-Mirugashira, Chitra, Danishta.

Mercury in Seventh Bhava:

Spouse is very young and intelligent. He / She is the youngest of the family. Spouse is an educated one. Love will appear after marriage. After the second child born, the native should buy plots and register document.

Jupiter in Seventh Bhava:

Spouse would come from royal family with good character. Spouse would equal to God. Seventh bhava Jupiter is so weak. So, the married life would be worse.

Venus in Seventh Bhava:

Spouse would be an attractive person like cinema star. After marriage money flow will increase. There is a change in character will come. It must a bad one. Enjoy sex very well.

Saturn in Seventh Bhava:

Late marriage is best. Male should marry after 30. Female should marry after 27. Matchless couple is best. After marriage poverty will come. Life partner should be poor or physically challenged person or over age or black colour is very best for happy married life.

Rahu in Seventh Bhava:

Late marriage is best. Other language, other state, other country spouse is very apt. After marriage accident or surgery would happen. Spouse house is located near main road or under the bridge.

Kethu in Seventh Bhava:

Spouse would be a spiritual person. Spouse has no interest. in intercourse. Friends and partners will cheat them. Second child will dealy. After marriage the native will face suit. No interest in family life. Separation would come.

Seventh Lord in 12 Bhavas:

Seventh Lord in Lagna:

Both husband and wife attract each other. Well known spouse would come from native home town. Spouse would be a relative one. Nuclear family is the best for them.

Seventh Lord in Second Bhava:

Spouse would be handsome / beautiful. Income will come from spouse. Spouse should manage family financial accounts. Spouse would always like to speak with native. Spouse would come from relative side.

Seventh Lord in Third Bhava:

Search spouse through police, broker and internet is the best option for them. Spouse look like more young. Spouse should write lyric and essays. TV station / Radio station / Post office / Police training center should locate near the spouse house.

Seventh Lord in Fourth Bhava:

Spouse has garden and farms. Well known person would come as a spouse. Graveyard would very near to the spouse's house. Avoid alcohol party in wedding function. Bus stand / Clinic should locate near the spouse house.

Seventh Lord in Fifth House:

Spouse would be the uncle or uncle's child. Spouse would come from teachers family or teacher would come as spouse. More chances for love marriage.

Seventh Lord in Sixth House:

Delayed marriage is best. Employee spouse should come. Buy loan for marriage is very important. Spouse would be a sick patient. Sexual desire never satisfied.

Seventh Lord in Own House:

Best spouse would come at the best time. Sexual desire would satisfy. After marriage financial growth is developed. Spouse should earn money. Spouse would be selfish. Gemini / Virgo / Sagittarius / Pisces lagna people should vigilant in their marriage.

Seventh Lord in Eighth House:

A secret is in wedding. A secret is with his / her spouse A fear in heart till marriage. After marriage the native should face accident / surgery or suit. Spouse may be a sick person. Couple never travel in two wheeler together. After marriage take LIC policy is best.

Seventh Lord in Ninth Bhava:

Spouse should be a teacher. Spouse should have good character. Temple, Mut, chatram should locate near the spouse house. Spouse should complete Ph.D research degree. Religion conversion may be done.

Seventh Lord in Tenth House:

Spouse should come from the work place. Doing business on behalf of spouse is very best. Do karma after marriage. After second child born, own business will form. Spouse should be in higher post.

Seventh Lord in Eleventh House:

Spouse should be elder than native. Spouse should be a greedy person. Spouse will set through friends. More chances for love marriage and also for second marriage. Blissful sexual life. Spouse has more friends.

Seventh Lord in Twelveth House:

Spouse belongs to other state, other country or more than 500 kilometers from home town is the very best. After marriage go to abroad is the very best. If kethu connects here no pleasure in family life.

Direction of the Life Partner:

S.No	Planet	Direction
1	If Sun connects with 7 th bhava or seventh lord, the spouse would come from	East Direction
2	If Moon connects with 7 th bhava or seventh lord, the spouse would come from	North west Direction
3	If Mars connects with 7 th bhava or seventh lord, the spouse would come from	South Direction
4	If Mercury connects with 7 th bhava or seventh lord, the spouse would come from	North Direction
5	If Jupiter connects with 7 th bhava or seventh lord, the spouse would come from	North east Direction
6	If Venus connects with 7 th bhava or seventh lord, the spouse would come from	South east Direction
7	If Saturn connects with 7 th bhava or seventh lord, the spouse would come from	West Direction
8	If Rahu connects with 7 th bhava or seventh lord, the spouse would come from	South west Direction
9	If Kethu connects with 7 th bhava or seventh lord, the spouse would come from	North east Direction

Only One Marriage:

Second and seventh house lords conjunction / aspect or Jupiter' aspect on second or seventh house lords ensure the native has only one marriage.

Two Marriage Yoga:

Second or Seventh house lord should weak and Mars Should Conjunction with Moon / kethu the native will Marry two husbands or two wives.

Three Marriage Yoga:

Fifth, Seventh, Eleventh bhava and their lords connects with each other by conjunction, aspect, exchange or standing star, the native will marry three husbands or three wives.

Conclusion:

Apart from dasa vitha porutham the strength of seventh bhava, the strength of seventh bhava lord, which planet occupies in the seventh bhava are very important in marriage matching.

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